

**EFFECT OF THE INTERFACE THERMAL CONTACT CONDUCTANCE
BETWEEN FIBER-MATRIX IN THE EFFECTIVE CONDUCTIVITY OF THE
FIBER COMPOSITES MATERIALS.**

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ABSTRACT

The structure and properties of the interphase fiber-matrix, influences notably the mechanics and thermal properties of composites materials. This paper, outlines a thermal analysis in steady state, with the purpose of studying the effect of the interface contact conductance fiber-matrix, on the effective conductivity of composite in normal directions to the fiber axes. The problem is presented in dimensionless form, and the numerical method employed is the F.E.M. Results show that the effect is more important in the cases with high volume fiber fraction and a high conductivity fiber-matrix ratio.

Keywords: composite materials, effective thermal conductivity, interface contact conductance

Notation

a,b= semidistance between
fibers centers in x and y
directions
 h_c = thermal contact conductance
coefficient
K = thermal conductivity
q = heat flow
R = fiber radius
T = temperature
 β = conductivity ratio
fiber/matrix

γ = arc tan b/a
v = fiber volume fraction
Subscripts:
e = effective value
f = of the fiber
m = of the matrix
x = on x direction
y = on y direction
Superscripts:
+ = dimensionless value

1. INTRODUCTION

An important area of research is the determination of properties of composite materials from the properties of the components. In this context, the structure and properties of the bonding fiber-matrix must be included, since fiber strongly influences the thermal properties of composite materials.

The problem of determining the effective thermal conductivity of composite materials began with studies which assumed a perfect bonding between the components. Springer and Tsai [1], proposed a approximation based in the analogy between the response of a unidirectional composite to longitudinal shear and to transverse heat transfer. Behrens [2], obtained general expressions, in integral form, for thermal conductivities of composite with orthorhombic symmetry. In the case of circular filaments in a square lattice composite, the expresion is

$$\frac{K_o}{K_m} = \frac{[(\beta + 1) + v(\beta - 1)]}{[(\beta + 1) - v(\beta - 1)]} \quad (1)$$

The above expresion is in agreement with the prediction of classical theory of Maxwell and Rayleigh, and hence is assumed that the thermal interaction among fibers is negligible, which implies that the model is valid for cases of low volume fraction values.

Several factors affect, favourably and unfavourably, the bonding fiber-matrix. Among the unfavourable factors, one of the more important is due to a large mismatch in the components thermal expansion coefficients. This problem was studied, by Powell et al. [3], for a composite of a hot-pressed glass matrix with a dispersed phase of spherical Nickel particles. In the experiment, when the composite was maintained near the manufacture temperature of 700°C, the measured effective thermal conductivity and diffusivity was in agreement with the prediction based in the Rayleigh-Maxwell theory. Nevertheless, when the composite was cooled, the thermal expansion mismatch lead to decohesion between the phases, and thermal conductivity and diffusivity values obtained are below those predicted by the theory. In this composite the effect of interfacial resistance is strong, making more specific, when it was cooled to room temperature, the relative decrease was about 50%.

The first theoretical study of effective thermal conductivity that includes the effect of the interface thermal conductance, or resistance, was presented by Hasselman and Johnson [4]. The problem was resolved proposing an adequate boundary condition at the interface to account to the thermal contact conductance h_c , in the original Rayleigh-Maxwell ecuations. A new particular solution was obtained, and the expresion for the efective thermal conductivity, yield:

$$\frac{K_o}{K_m} = \frac{[(\beta - 1 - \frac{K_f}{Rh_c})v + (1 + \beta + \frac{K_f}{Rh_c})]}{[(1 - \beta + \frac{K_f}{Rh_c})v + (1 + \beta + \frac{K_f}{Rh_c})]} \quad (2)$$

For $h_c \rightarrow \infty$, equation (2) agrees with (1). Both equations are only valid for low volume dispersions fraction.

Han and Cosner [5], presented a complete study of effective conductivity when the proximity effects of embedded fibers are significant, and hence, with high volume fibers fraction. In these cases, the geometrical fibers arrangement parameters are very influential. However, this model cannot account thermal contact conductance, since at the interface between fiber and matrix, the equalities of the temperature and the normal heat fluxes, are proposed in the analysis method.

In this paper we focus on effective thermal conductivity of fibrous composites in the normal direction to the fiber axes. The model proposed accounts, first, the thermal interaction due to the proximity of the fibers, and second, the bonding between components. This bonding is modeled by a coefficient h_c of thermal contact conductance, and its effect on the effective conductivity is considered. The results obtained are contrasted, first, with the Hans and Cosner model, for $h_c \rightarrow \infty$ and several geometrical parameters values, and second, with the Hasselman and Johnson model, for low values of v , and several values of h_c .

2. ANALYSIS

For the composite, we assume that the fibers, with thermal conductivity K_f , are long circular cylinders, of radius R , dispersed uniformly in the matrix, with conductivity K_m . Two array types are considered: rectangular and staggered. The semidistance between the fibers centers in the x and y directions, are denoted by a and b respectively -Figure 1-. The boundary conditions for the region of interest, are formulated in section 2.1. In section 2.2., the problem is reformulated in nondimensional form, and is numerically resolved by the Finite Element Method in section 2.3. The derivation of effective thermal conductivity is described in section 2.4.

Figure 1. Region of interest of composite, and boundary conditions.

2.1. Boundary Conditions

When the composite is subjected to a heat flow transverse to the fibers axes of, due to different conductivities of components, a two dimensional heat conduction problem in steady-state is formulated. The region of interest for the thermal analysis, is the rectangle indicated -Figure 1-. If the fibers are dispersed uniformly, and if the thermal contact conductance is a constant value (Finite or infinite) in overall interphase, then the boundary conditions at the sides of the rectangle, are identical to those exposed by Han and Cosner [5], and hence, the sides $x=0$ and $x=a$, are insulated, and the sides $y = b$ and $y = 0$ are of constant temperature, denoted by T_1 and T_2 , ($T_1 > T_2$) respectively.

At the interface $r=R$, there is a thermal contact conductance, h_c , and hence the interface condition is :

$$-K_m \frac{\partial T_m}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_0} = h_c [T_m (R_0, \phi) - T_f (R_0, \phi)] = -K_f \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_0} \quad (3)$$

2.2. Dimensionless Formulation

The following dimensionless variables are introduced:

$$T^+ = \frac{T - T_2}{T_1 - T_2} ; \quad x^+ = \frac{x}{a} ; \quad y^+ = \frac{y}{a} \quad (4)$$

The news boundary conditions, are :

$$\begin{aligned} T^+ (x^+, b/a) = 1 & ; \quad T^+ (x^+, 0) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial T^+}{\partial x^+} \Big|_{x^+=0} = 0 & ; \quad \frac{\partial T^+}{\partial x^+} \Big|_{x^+=1} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

with the previous variables, the new dimensionless polar coordinate is $r^+ = r/a$, and at the interface $r^+ = R/a = R^+$, the conditions is:

$$-\frac{\partial T_m^+}{\partial r^+} \Big|_{r^+=R^+} = h_c^+ [T_m^+ (R^+, \phi) - T_f^+ (R^+, \phi)] = -\beta \frac{\partial T_f^+}{\partial r^+} \Big|_{r^+=R^+} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } h_c^+ = h_c \frac{a}{K_m} ; \quad \beta = \frac{K_f}{K_m}$$

In this study, we consider the effect of the dimensionless group h_c^+ . We note that for composite with high values of fiber fraction v , and for the typical fiber diameter used (about 2 o 3 microns), the real values of h_c are much higher than the dimensionless values of h_c^+ .

2.3. Analysis by F.E.M.

In this work, the Finite Element Method is employed to solve the two dimensional heat conduction problem. In Figure 2(a), the discretization is presented. Two types of elements [6] are used. The first is a linear element of four (or three) nodal points, and has a single degree of freedom temperature, at each node, and is used to discretize the two dimensional region of each component -Figure 2(a)-. The second, is a link element with two nodal points located, in this case, at coincident positions. The theoretical formulation for this link element may be written as :

$$q = hA(T(i) - T(j)) \quad (7)$$

where $T(i)$, $T(j)$ are the node temperature.

The normal use of this type of element is for boundaries with convection transfer, but in this case it can be use to the numerical simulation of the interface condition (6) between the fiber-matrix.

The simple elements and grid used, are enough to provide a good accuracy to compare the results with previous studies. As an example, the Figure 2, illustrates the aproximate solution $T^+(x^+, y^+)$ for a case with $\nu = 0.6$, $\beta = 10$, simetrical ($\gamma = 45^\circ$) and rectangular array. In the Figure 2(b), the coefficient $h_c^+ \rightarrow \infty$, and in the Figure 2(c), $h_c^+ = 10$. In the first case the results agree with those obtained by Han and Cosner [6]. In the second case, the effect of a finite value of h_c in the temperature distribution is clearly appreciated. Note that in this example, the value of ν is high.

Figure 2. (a) Discretization by F.E.M. Temperature field, rectangular array (b) $h_c^+ = \infty$, and (c) $h_c^+ = 10$; $\beta = 10$; $\nu = 0.6$, $\gamma = 45$ deg.

2.4. Effective Thermal Conductivity

Once the conduction problem is resolved, we can evaluate the effective or equivalent conductivity. If the main heat flow is in the y direction, then the effective conductivity, K_{ey} , is obtained from :

$$q_y^+ = \frac{K_{ey}}{K_m} \tan \gamma \quad (8)$$

where, q_y^+ is the heat flow evaluated from the integration of $\partial T^+/\partial y^+$ over the corresponding boundary, and $\tan \gamma = a/b$. To evaluate K_{ex} only a change in the boundary conditions is required, and yields :

$$q_x^+ = \frac{K_{ex}}{K_m} \frac{1}{\tan \gamma} \quad (9)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained are presented to show the effect of interface contact conductance on the effective conductivity of the composite, especially in cases with high fiber volume fraction values ($v = 0.7, 0.6$). Nevertheless, one case of low volume fraction is considered ($v = 0.25$) to be compare with a valid model in this range.

In Figure 3(a), the effective conductivity ratio K_e/K_m is represented, versus the components conductivity ratio β . The high v value is 0.7, $\gamma = 45^\circ$ and the fiber array is rectangular. The effect of dimensionless h_c^+ is an important drop of the effective conductivity. The curve with $h_c^+ = \infty$, agrees with the obtained by Han and Cosner [5]. The curves of Figure 3(b) depict the quotient between the preceding curves, with a finite value of h_c^+ , and the curve with $h_c^+ = \infty$. This curves provide the relative effect of h_c^+ in the effective conductivity. This effect is clearly less pronounced in the cases with low fiber volume fraction values as can be seen in Figure 6(b). Similar curves have been obtained for $v = 0.6$, $\gamma = 45^\circ$, in Figures 4(a)-(b), but in this case the fiber array is staggered.

In the preceding cases, $\gamma = 45^\circ$, and hence, the effective conductivity does not depend on the direction. In Figures 5(a)-(b), a case with $\gamma = 50^\circ$, $v = 0.6$, and a rectangular array is considered. The effective conductivities in x and y directions, are very different. As is clear, the rectangular arrangement is more anisotropic than the staggered one. For details, see reference [5].

The case with low fiber volume fraction values, correspond to figures 6(a)-(b). The curves obtained by F.E.M., are in agreement with the analytical expression (2) of Hasselman and Johnson.

In all cases presented, the effect of the interface contact conductance is more important when the ratio between components conductivities is large. This is due to the radial component of the temperature gradient at the interface, wich is very large compared to the transversal component. The value range of β here considered varies from 1 to 100. For $\beta < 1$, the effect of the interface conductance in the fibrous composite is negligible. This case is the opposite to the latter, and hence, the principal contribution to the gradient is due to the transversal component. For this reason, in this study it was not included. In the figures depicted, we can see, that the effect of h_c is very little in proximity to $\beta = 1$.

Fig.3.(a) Effective conductivity, rectangular array, $v=0.7$, $\gamma=45^\circ$;(b) Relative effect of h^+ .

Fig.4.(a) Effective conductivity, staggered array, $v=0.6$, $\gamma=45^\circ$;(b) Relative effect of h^+ .

Fig.5. Effective conductivity, rect. array, $v=0.6$, $\gamma=50^\circ$.(a) In x direction.(b) In y direction.

Fig.6.(a) Effective conductivity, rectangular array, $v=0.25$, $\gamma=45^\circ$;(b)Relative effect of h^+ .

4. CONCLUSIONS

The following are the conclusion arrived at in this paper:

- 1) The effect of interface contact conductance in the effective conductivity in the normal direction to the fiber axes, is an important reduction of this global property.
- 2) The magnitude of this effect is unequal, and more significant in the following cases:
 - a) When the conductivity fiber-conductivity matrix ratio is high.
 - b) When the fiber volume fraction is high.
- 3) If further the previous cases, the nature of boundary fiber-matrix is dependent on temperature, this effect, also can contribute to an strong dependence of global properties with the temperature.
- 4) The model proposed in this paper can be useful as a guide for the study of the behaviour composites, but the strong sensibility for parameters, such us the arrangement fiber, fiber radius, the nature of bonding fiber-matrix, etc..., force us to consider a subsequent study, that can determine the upper and lower bounds of the effective thermal conductivity.

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